

ADIYAN, ARANADAN, ERAVALLAN, HILL PULAYA AND IRULAR- A SOCIOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF TRIBAL COMMUNITIES IN KERALA

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Abstract

A socio economic survey of Scheduled Tribes was conducted during 2008-10 with the participation of local bodies having Scheduled Tribe population. The survey has revealed that the population of Scheduled Tribes has increased from 3,64,189 in 2001 to 4,26,208 in 2008-10. Technically, the decadal growth of Scheduled Tribes works out to 17.03 per cent, where as the growth of the general population during 2001-11 is only 4.86 per cent. The inconsistency is due to inclusion/exclusion process explained above. Still the representation of Scheduled Tribes to the total population of the State is only 1.28 per cent.

Wayanad District stands first with 35.94 per cent of the Scheduled Tribe population of the State, followed by Idukki (12.42%), Kasaragod (11.21%) and Palakkad (11.01%) Districts. As usual, Alappuzha stands as the lowest district of Scheduled Tribe population with a representation of only 0.71 per cent of the population.

The Scheduled Tribes in Wayanad constitutes 18.76 per cent of the total population of the district. As such they are a decisive fraction in the policy framing of the district as well as the State. In Idukki, the district with the second largest population, the Scheduled Tribes are only 4.78 per cent of the district population. In Alappuzha, the share of Scheduled Tribes in the district population is only 0.14 per cent. Approximately 71 per cent of the Scheduled Tribes in Kerala are in four districts, namely; Wayanad, Idukki, Kasaragod and Palakkad.

Key Words: Scheduled Tribes, Wayanad, Adiyar, Aranadan, Eravallan, Hill Pulaya and Irular.

Introduction

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The district wise population of Scheduled Tribes is shown in Table 2.1

District	Population	Per centage of ST
Thiruvananthapuram	17185	4.03
Kollam	4641	1.09
Pathanamthitta	6379	1.59
Alappuzha	3014	0.71
Kottayam	16764	3.93
Idukki	52913	12.42
Eranakulam	8936	2.10

Thrissur	5561	1.31
Palakkad	46948	11.01
Malappuram	14496	3.40
Kozhikode	10627	2.49
Wayanad	153181	35.94
Kannur	37772	8.86
Kasaragod	47791	11.21
:Total	426208	100

The total families of Scheduled Tribes in Kerala are enumerated as 1,07,965 spread over in all the districts of the State. Wayanad District has 36,135 Scheduled Tribe families (33.47%) followed by 14,315 families (13.26%) in Idukki, 13,223 families (12.25%) in Palakkad and 11598 families (10.74%) in Kasaragod. Seventy eight per cent of Scheduled Tribe families in the State are located in five districts, namely; Wayanad, Idukki, Palakkad, Kasaragod and Kannur.

Table 2.2 District wise Number of Families

Sl.No.	District	Families	%
1	Thiruvananthapuram	5183	4.80
2	Kollam	1303	1.21
3	Pathanamthitta	1791	1.66
4	Alappuzha	872	0.81
5	Kottayam	4353	4.03
6	Idukki	14315	13.26
7	Eranakulam	2370	2.20
8	Thrissur	1481	1.37
9	Palakkad	13223	12.25
10	Malappuram	3656	3.39
11	Kozhikode	2680	2.48
12	Wayanad	36135	33.47
13	Kannur	9005	8.34
14	Kasaragod	11598	10.74

Tribal Communities and Their Population Characteristics.

1. Adiyar

Adiyar families are concentrated mainly in Wayanad District. About 99.80 per cent of the Adiyar population is settled in Wayanad District alone. A few families/persons have moved on to Kottayam, Idukki, Kozhikode and Ernakulam Districts;

In Wayanad District, Adiyars are found in 9 Grama Panchayats. However, their sizable population is seen in four Grama Panchayats, namely; Thirunelly (5089), Mananthavady (3113), Panamaram (1871) and Pulpally (860). About 45.35 per cent of Adiyar community is found in Thirunelly Grama Panchayat. Eloor Municipality in Ernakulam District is the only urban area where 5 Adiyar families are settled.

There are 2576 Adiyar families in the State, of which 2570 are in Wayanad District. Adiyar population numbers 11,221 consisting of 5389 males and 5822 females, registering the sex ratio of the community as 1000 : 1082. The family size of Adiyar community is 4.35, which is higher than the state average.

Adiyars used to be bonded to their land lords till the enforcement of the Abolition of Bonded Labour Act of 1976. They are now marginal agriculturists but majority are agricultural labourers. Now a days they migrate to Karnataka to work in agricultural farms. '*Gaddika*' is a famous art form of Adiyar community.

Adiyars are bilingual. They speak a separate dialect of Kannada known as '*Adiyabhasha*'. Adiyar literally means 'slave or serf' in Malayalam. They call themselves as '*Ravulavar*'. The community is divided into a number of clans called '*Mantu*' or '*Chemman*' and the clan head is known as '*Chemmakkar*'. The children take their mother's clan. '*Chemmakkar*' regulates the life cycle rites of the clan. The hamlets are uniethnic and the head is known as '*Kuntumooan*' who settles disputes among members. The religious rites are officiated by '*Kannaladi*'. The '*Nadumooan*' or '*Peruman*' controls the regional affairs of the community.

The details on Adiyar families and population in districts are shown in Table 2.3

(1)	(2)	(3 Families)	(4) Male	(5) Female	(6) Total	(7) %
1	Kottayam :	-	-	1	1	-
2	Idukki :	-	2	-	2	0.01
3	Eranakulam :	5	8	11	19	0.16
4	Kozhikode :	1	2	1	3	0.03
5	Wayanad :	2570	5377	5819	11196	99.80
Total		2576	5389	5832	11221	100

2. Aranadan (Arandan)

Aranadan community is found only in the Nilambur forests of Malappuram District. The community name is derived from two local terms, 'Aravam' means snake and 'Nadan' means countrymen. They are one of the diminutive tribal communities. Their language is found to be a mixture of Malayalam, Tamil and Tulu.

Aranadans are endogamous with subdivisions called 'Villa'(clan). Each settlement has a headman called 'Chemmakkaran' who settles disputes and officiates in the rituals connected with their life cycle. 'Kalladikaran' acts as the priest cum healer.

Aranadans are believed to be the original inhabitants of the erstwhile Eranad Taluk of Malappuram District. They were expert hunters and food gatherers with little interest in agriculture and cattle rearing. They used to hunt pythons and extract oil which was used as a remedy for leprosy. They also collect minor forest produces. The deforestation and strict enforcement of Forest Laws have threatened their livelihood pattern. The community as a whole is very backward in terms of social and economic status.

There are 80 families of Aranadan community with population of 247, consisting of 107 males and 140 females. The family size is 3.08 which is below the state average. As the females outnumber the males, the sex ratio of Aranadan community is abnormally high i.e., 1000 : 1308.

In Malappuram, the community is spread over in 8 Grama Panchayats, namely; Muthedam, Vazhikkadavu, Edakkara, Pothukallu(Nilambur Block Panchayat), Amarambalam, Karulai, Kalikavu and Chokkad(Kalikave Block Panchayat).

3. Eravallan

Earlier the Eravallans were known as '*Villu Vedan*', which means hunters using bows and arrows. In early Dravidian Language '*Eravan*' is related to agricultural serfs. Among themselves they speak a crude dialect of Tamil but to others they can speak Malayalam.

The institution of headman is called '*Talaivan*' and over a period of continuous subjugation the relevance of headman is not there and as a result the '*Pujari*' (priest) performs the duties of headman.

Eravallans are landless agricultural labourers attached to the local landlords. They are experts in ploughing dry lands for the cultivation of various crops. Caste discrimination is high in their locality.

There are 1255 families belonging to Eravallan community as identified in the survey. The community has 2210 males and 2208 females, registering their population as 4418. Since the male members are more than the females, the sex ratio is 1000 : 999, which is far below the state average of 1000 : 1031. The family size works out to 3.52

Altogether 1254 families of Eravallan community are distributed in 7 Grama Panchayats in Palakkad District. The total population in the 7 Grama Panchayats is 4412. Majority of them are settled in Muthalamada (2159), Perumatty(1497) and Kozhinjampara (465) Grama Panchayats. Others are located in Pattanchery, Nalleppilly, Eruthiampathy and Elavanchery Grama Panchayats. Nearly, 49 per cent of Eravallan families are settled in Muthalamada Grama Panchayat. One family, with six members of Eravallan community has been identified in Melukavu Grama Panchayat, Kottayam District.

4. Hill Pulaya

(Mala Pulayan, Kurumba Pulayan, Karavazhi Pulayan, Pamba Pulayan)

Hill Pulayas are found only in Idukki District. They are mainly concentrated in Kanthallur and Marayur Grama Panchayats. The population of Hill Pulaya in these two grama panchayats comes to 1797 and 1436 respectively. In Chinnakanal Grama Panchayat their population is 171. In Kattappana and Santhanpara Grama Panchayats also there are scattered Hill Pulayas. Hill Pulayas have 960 families with population of 3415. Their family size is 3.56. There are 1709 males and 1706 females in the community and hence the sex ratio works out to 1000 : 998, which is below the state average.

Hill Pulayas are divided into three endogamous sects, viz; Kurumba Pulayan, Karavazhi Pulayan and Pamba Pulayan. Kurumba Pulayans are found only in the '*Anchunad*' area of Devikulam Taluk of Idukki District. They are early immigrants from Tamil Nadu. Kurumba Pulayans consider themselves superior in social status to the other two sects. The settlements of these three groups are separate. Kurumba Pulayans are seen in forest areas while the Karavazhi Pulayans are found in plain areas of Marayur and Kanthallur Grama Panchayats. Pamba Pulayans are seen in Chinnar Wildlife Sanctuary area in Idukki District. All of them speak a dialect of Tamil with a few Malayalam words too.

Kurumba Pulayan community has their headman called '*Arasan*'. The head man of Karavazhi Pulayan is '*Kudumban*'. He has assistants and executives known under various names like '*Varijan*' and '*Kolkkaran*' respectively.

Kurumba Pulayan community were food gatherers and hunters and practised slash and burn cultivation. They cultivate lemon grass and extract oil. They are found to be experts in sheep rearing. On the other hand Karavazhi Pulayans are landless agricultural serfs under the Caste Hindus. Currently both these two major sections are engaged in casual labour.

Karavazhi Pulayans have many colourful forms of folk dances and they believe that dancing pleases the Gods and better blessings would be granted. They have had the opportunity to present their folk songs and dances in national forums.

5. Irular, Irulan

Irular community is distributed in Palakkad District and they are mainly concentrated in Attappady region. They are also found in Tamil Nadu. They have a dialect of their own called 'Irula bhasha', which has more affinity to Tamil.

Their traditional social organisation is endowed with various functionaries, namely; '*Ooru Moopan*' (Chieftain), '*Bhandari*' (Treasurer), '*Kuruthala*' (assistant to Chieftain) '*Mannukaran*' (soil expert), '*Marunnukaran*' (healer) etc. These positions are hereditary and succession is by the son. This traditional institutions play a decisive role in the social control mechanism of Irular community.

Earlier Irular were hunters, gatherers and shifting cultivators. Now they have become experts in settled agriculture and also work as agricultural labourers. The major area in Attappady falls under rain shadow region and as such the important crops raised by them under dry farming are '*Ragi*', '*Chama*', '*Thina*', '*Cholam*', '*Thuvara*', '*Kadala*' etc. For cultivation they stay away from their hamlet and erect temporary huts. Irular community has attractive songs and dances which tell about their forest, cultivation, emotions etc.

They have been empowered through '*Thaikula Sangham*', exclusively for women and '*Ooruvikasana Samithi*' organised under the Attappady Hills Area Development Society. Their livelihood means have been affected due to the influx of non tribal population both from other parts of Kerala and Tamil Nadu.

Technically, Irular community has representation in four districts, namely; Palakkad, Thiruvananthapuram, Idukki and Malappuram. There are 7617 families of Irular community, of which 7614 are in Palakkad District and one each in the other three districts. The family size of Irular community is 3.48

Irular population comes to 26,525. They have the credit of being the fifth largest community of Scheduled Tribes in Kerala. They constitute 6.22 per cent of the Scheduled Tribes. In Palakkad they are settled in 10 Grama Panchayats, with the concentration in the 3 Grama Panchayats of Attappady region. Approximately 95.20 per cent of Irular community is located in

Agali (9474), Sholayur (9076) and Pudur (6703) Grama Panchayats of Attappady. Pudussery (907) and Malampuzha (245) are the other two Grama Panchayats with a sizable population of Irular community. Since the population consists of 13163 males and 13362 females, the sex ratio of Irular community is 1000 : 1015.

The details of Irular population in the districts are shown in Table 2.4.

Table 2.4

District	Male	Female		Total	(%) %
Thiruvananthapuram	1	1	3	4	0.01
Idukki	1	1	4	5	0.01
Malappuram	1	3	1	4	0.01
Palakkad	7614	13158	13354	26512	99.97
Total	7617	13163	13362	26525	100

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